

Recent Advances of Propagation Channel Research for 6G Wireless Communication Systems

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Abstract—Channel is the primary building block of wireless communication system between the transmitter and receivers. Measuring, characterizing, and modeling channels are of significant importance for network modeling, system deployment, and theoretical analysis of communication systems. Next-generation networks such as sixth-generation (6G) will bring new enabling technologies (THz), multiple mobilities (high-speed train (HST), UAV trajectory), and architectures (3D network, integrated terrestrial-non terrestrial network) which ought to cater to channel propagation characteristics. Accurate channel models that combine different technologies and disciplines can capture these channel characteristics play a critical role in designing and testing the future 6G system. In this article, we overview the characteristics, measurement, and modeling of 6G wireless channels. Also, we provide a summary of recent advances in channel research of 6G. Finally, we outline the research challenges, open issues, and future direction of channel models and characteristics in 6G wireless communications.

Index Terms—3D; 6DoF; 6G; B5G; Channel; THz.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world is now embarking into the beyond fifth-generation (B5G) or sixth-generation (6G) mobile communications epoch [1], which will be wholly digital, enabling smartly enhanced mobile broadband connectivity and intelligent infrastructures to cater for the foreseen upsurge in mobile data. Our way of life is continuously changing with technological drive and requirements. It prompts us to satisfy the continued pursuance to send more data, more rapidly, and of course, more effectively over the air. For example, it is expected that the total world traffic in mobile devices monthly will be about 164 exabytes (EB) in 2025, which is more than five times the traffic in 2019 (about 33 EB). Among various data traffic, video will be predominant. The lion's share of mobile traffic is already made up of video traffic. For instance, in 2019, a significant portion of mobile traffic was video (63 percent), which is foreseen to increase in the coming years (e.g., the prediction is about 76 percent in 2025). This trait will continue to flourish even after reaching the 5G milestone in 2020, with B5G/6G mobile networks expecting to hold up significantly higher capacity (throughput) per device (up to terabits per second). To do that, there needs to be a dawn of a new generation of mobile technology in every decade since the inception of the mobile cellular standards [2]. Table I presents a key summary of different generations of mobile technology with the evolution towards 6G.

Moreover, 6G will conform to a new network architecture which would also expand the breadth and depth of communication coverage. The existing 4G and 5G network architecture is based on legacy terrestrial infrastructure, which has the following two drawbacks [3]. i) lack of architectural integrations of the high-altitude (space and air) and communication (sea and underwater) scenarios, which is necessary for future services; ii) exorbitantly expensive provisioning cost for ultra-dense cellular networks to furnish pervasive connectivity on the global scale. In order to compensate for the aforementioned shortcomings, 6G will integrate non-terrestrial networks to provide full wireless coverage. Fig. 1 illustrates the envisioned scenarios for 6G space-air-ground-sea-underwater (SAGSU) integrated architecture. That means 6G architecture will be a 3D network architecture that consists of a 5-space domain.

Fig. 1. Envisioned 6G architecture: ubiquitous 3D SAGSU coverage

A thorough study of 6G wireless channels is required to materialize and understand the envisioned 6G architecture. Analyzing and realizing wireless channels are at the forefront for network planning, deployment, and performance evaluation of 6G networks. Moreover, channel modeling research helps us attain necessary information of inbuilt statistical properties between transmitters and receivers in 6G wireless networks. In 6G wireless systems, channel measurement, modeling and

TABLE I
CRITICAL SUMMARY OF DIFFERENT GENERATIONS OF MOBILE COMMUNICATION [2].

Generation	Operational year	Peak data rate	Wireless access	Core network	Key services
1G	1984	2.4 kbit/s	Analog	Circuit-based	Mobile telephony
2G	1991	64 kbit/s	Digital	Circuit-based	Digital voice, short messages
3G	2002	2 Mbit/s	Digital	Circuit and packet-based	Internet
4G	2012	100 Mbit/s	Digital	Fully IP-based	Internet of Applications
5G	2020	20 Gbit/s	Digital	Fully IP-based	Internet of Things
6G	2030	1 Tbit/s	Digital	Fully IP-based	Internet of Everything

characteristics analysis must incorporate various enabling technologies and disciplines [4], such as —

- **seamless global coverage** → satellite, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), terrestrial, ultra-dense network (UDN), maritime, underwater acoustic communication;
- **more channels** → ultra-massive MIMO, spatial modulation, orbital angular momentum (OAM), new waveforms: F-OFDM/UFMC/FBMC, multiple mobilities: high-speed train (HST)/V2V/D2D, multiple access: NOMA, industrial IoT, VR/AR/MR, wearable displays, mobile robots, and drones;
- **more bandwidth** → millimeter wave (mmWave), terahertz (THz), optical wireless, unlicensed access/cognitive radio network, full duplex, multi-standard systems;
- **more power efficiency** → small cells, green communications, advanced modulation and coding: Polar code, Network coding;
- **less noise** → filtering and
- **less interference** → interference randomization, interference coordination, interference cancellation, interference alignment.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of some salient features of 6G channel characteristics. Section III summarizes channel measurement and model approach for several 6G enabling technologies and applications such as THz, an extremely high mobile scenario of HST, usage of artificial intelligence (AI). Several seminal articles with recent advances of 6G channel research are elaborated in Section IV. Section V discusses future research issues and challenges of the 6G channel phenomenon, followed by the concluding remarks in Section VI.

II. KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF 6G CHANNEL

Fig. 2 demonstrates several salient channel properties for 6G communication systems. These properties are higher path loss, noise effect (atmospheric and sky [5]), specular power angular spectrum, sparse channel impulse response (CIR), fading behavior is, among others. Although these fundamental channel properties align with the Yester generation of mobile technology, they have more impact for 6G channel modeling than before. For example, THz frequency plays a large part in designing a 6G system. Using frequencies above 0.1 THz, which means 0.1 THz to 10 THz, new propagation phenomena can appear, such as reflection, wave absorption by some molecules, and channel noise generation [5], [6]. The realization of the Terahertz band appears to be essential to design systems exploiting this frequency range. Thus, academy researchers and industry stakeholders are focusing

on the behavior of THz wave traversing various scenarios, environments, and in the presence of items such as walls (be it concrete or wooden) or grass.

Fig. 2. Salient key 6G channel properties.

For example, in the 6G THz channel in addition to spreading loss, molecular absorption loss is also included. The spreading loss can be given as [5]

$$s_{Loss}(f, d) = \left(\frac{c}{4\pi d}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

f is the carrier frequency, d is the distance between transmitter and receiver, c is the velocity of light. For absorption loss, several parameters such as temperature, pressure, and distance are responsible. The absorption loss can be expressed as follows [5]

$$abs_{Loss}(f, d) = e^{-K(f)d}, \quad (2)$$

where $K(f)$ is the total absorption coefficient. The value of $K(f)$ is calculated from the HITRAN database [7]. The resultant path loss, therefore, is as follows—

$$PL = s_{Loss}(f, d) \times abs_{Loss}(f, d) = \left(\frac{c}{4\pi d}\right)^2 e^{-K(f)d}. \quad (3)$$

III. CHANNEL MEASUREMENTS AND MODEL OF 6G WIRELESS SYSTEM

Channel measurements and modeling are very delicate processes. These two processes are intertwined and play a significant role in the communication channel designing process. To initiate the channel measurement process, we first define target scenarios. Fig. 3 (a) presents the canonical approach of channel measurement and modeling [8]. These approaches are also relevant for channel modeling for THz-enabled 6G wireless communication systems such as THz-enabled communication, extremely high mobile HST network, and so on. Channel measurements, after defining communications scenarios, channel measurements are then carried out. The next step is channel modeling, consisting of various types

of channel simulations—deterministic, stochastic, and hybrid channel modeling. Deterministic channel modeling includes ray tracing, which is carried out for in-depth scenario description and the location between transmitter (TX) and Receiver (RX). Hence, the ray-tracing simulation is site-dependent. Stochastic channel modeling is created to facilitate model generation further and generalize the results. These models are derived and fed back using large-scale ray-tracing simulation results input and channel statistics.

(a) Conventional approach for 6G THz channel modeling

(b) Design process of 6G HST channel modeling

Fig. 3. Design process of 6G channel measurement and modeling approach [8], [9].

Channel measurement mainly relies on data. These data act as credible data sources and helps us to reflect realistic and pragmatic channel information. Furthermore, channel measurement data creates a workflow—obtain channel measurement data extraction of channel parameters then channel models can be established. For instance, the channel models 5G HST communication for lower mmWave frequency bands are created from extensive channel measurements [10]. Novel channel sounding systems are essential to obtain channel measurements data for better design and evaluate the future 6G HST communication systems. The currently available channel measurements for HST scenarios are mainly at few at mmWave bands. In [9], the authors develop a novel mmWave massive MIMO HST channel model for the B5G system. Fig. 3 (b) presents this new design process of 6G channel measurement and modeling approach that introduces novel 6G space-time-frequency non-stationarity.

As mentioned above, channel measurements and modeling deal with lots of data. Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the envisioned tools for future 6G networks [11], which highly relies on data and data training. In 6G, AI will be used to predict wireless channel properties over conventional channel modeling schemes. Fig. 4 demonstrates channel measurements and modeling for the 6G system utilizing AI. An increase of frequency bands (mmWave to THz), novel use cases,

innovative complex scenarios, and antenna elements will eventually spur data-driven solutions over the traditional system. AI helps by dividing and training huge data, such as multipath component (MPC) clustering, scenario classification, and channel prediction, using clustering, classification, and regression algorithms [4] as depicted in Fig. 4. AI techniques such as generative adversarial network (GAN) [12] can be applied to predict wireless channel statistics, thus helping channel modeling, including massive data.

Fig. 4. Design process channel measurement and modeling approach for AI-enabled 6G [4].

IV. RESEARCH ADVANCES OF 6G CHANNEL RESEARCH

In this section, we provide a summary of recent research advances on propagation channels for 6G wireless communication systems. These are research articles meticulously selected that offer a futuristic step for 6G propagation channel research. Various criteria such as frequency band, scenario, channel measurement techniques, and channel modeling techniques are included in the summary presented in Table II.

In [14], the authors provide channel characterization for mmWave vehicular communication for B5G networks. Although mmWave is already envisioned for 5G networks, but for V2V networks in B5G mmWave will also be used. Since molecular absorption is too much in THz compare to mmWave, mmWave would also be a good option for B5G/6G vehicular communication system.

In [9], the authors provide an in-depth overview of channel measurements for B5G HST communication. Different scenarios, train speeds, key channel statistics, and higher frequency bands such as mmWave and THz are used for the HST channel measurement. A novel HST channel model is also developed to analyze the non-stationarity of the mmWave frequency incorporating massive MIMO channel characteristics. The insightful analysis of this work can be beneficial to design and implement more precise HST channel models. In addition to that, developed HST channel sounder also helps to set up future B5G/6G THz channel measurements.

One step further, the authors in [15] explore the potentialities of the channel model of the more advanced intelligent transportation systems (ITSs) with improved safety and efficiency. Although they use mmWave as carrier frequency, they provide insight for the B5G network as well. The central focal point of their investigation is directional V2V channel measurements performed in the 60-GHz band. This work can

TABLE II
SUMMARY OF RECENT RESEARCH ADVANCES ON PROPAGATION CHANNEL FOR 6G.

Paper	Frequency band		Scenario				Channel measurement		Channel model		
	THz	mmWave	Indoor	Outdoor	Vehicular		Channel Sounder		Deterministic	Stochastic	Hybrid
					V2V	HST	Time domain	Frequency domain (VNA)			
[13]	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
[14]	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
[9]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
[15]	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
[8]	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
[16]	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
[4]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
[17]	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No

leverage their channel measurement setup and modeling for 6G THz channel research, which can be developed for various ITS channel scenario and channel statistics.

THz is envisioned as one of the enabling technology for 6G. Therefore, to make THz into a 6G reality, we need to know the underlying properties of the THz channel model. Article [13] renders a concise and thought-provoking study about THz channel modeling based on the deterministic, statistical, and hybrid (combination of stochastic and deterministic) methods. Moreover, the authors have described the in-depth characterization of ultra-massive MIMO for THz. Key physical parameters and the implications of different types of channel modeling methods for THz are also discussed.

Next, [8] provides an essential technical insight for B5G/6G THz channel modeling research around 300 GHz. The authors pointed out that the primary barrier of the THz channel modeling for 6G wireless systems is the unfavorable channel characteristics, which include very sensitivity of molecular absorption. In this work, the researchers provide a glimpse of the world's first THz communication standard (IEEE Standard 802.15.3d-2017), including a channel-modeling document (CMD) [18]. According to the CMD, in light of IEEE Standard 802.15.3d-2017, which is a standard for THz indoor applications, this work extensively elaborates THz channel modeling. Notwithstanding different THz channel modeling approaches such as deterministic and stochastic modeling also discussed. There are four indoor applications for the 6G THz scenario is provided along with channel-measurement technologies. Very high bandwidth of up to 69.12 GHz is also used for their channel measurement and modeling. In addition to the existing THz channel characteristics (molecular absorption effects, fast fading behavior, frequency selectivity, very high path loss), specular power angular spectrum (PAS) and sparse channel impulse response (CIR) have also been investigated.

Vertical heterogeneous network (V-HetNet) 3D architecture [19] is the new normal for next-generation 6G wireless communication systems such as 6G. As aligned with Fig. 1 (the envisioned 5-spatial 6G architecture), V-HetNet combines different communication systems in the various space domain, including space-to-underwater. As THz offers a huge swathe of

bandwidth, the channel measurement study in [16] reveals THz communications' true potential in V-HetNets. The authors in [10] also project those novel approaches considering channel behavior should be adopted from satellite to in-vivo THz communications for the coming 6G system.

Last but not least, both articles [4] and [17] provide an in-depth overview of 6G wireless channel measurements, characteristics, and models (ray tracing and the GBSM can serve as the standard deterministic and stochastic modeling methods) for all frequency bands for SAGSU scenarios. In particular, focusing on mmWave, terahertz, and optical wireless communication channels under all spectra; HST, V2V, ultra-massive MIMO, orbital angular momentum (OAM), and industrial Internet of Things (IoT) communication channels under full application scenarios. by considering individual channel characteristics for most 6G channels.

V. CHALLENGES, OPEN ISSUES AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Despite recent research advances there are numerous valid and significant challenges remain for 6G channel measurements and modeling.

A. Challenges for 3GPP Satellite Channel Modeling

In [20], 3GPP has standardized several instructions and specifications for characterizing mmWave satellite channel for 5G. However, second-order statistics nor the impact of Doppler, fading, and multipath components are not fully investigated by 3GPP yet. Notwithstanding, the satellite channel model for THz frequency is still in its infancy. In addition, a general and precise model of a fully layered space-air-ground channel is still not available.

B. Six Degree of Freedom (6DoF) Channel Modeling for 6G THz Indoor Network

6G indoor scenarios overwhelmingly consist of a THz communication system. It includes handheld devices, augmented reality contact lenses, the internet of Bio nano things (IoBNT), nanobots, and so on [21]. Perfect alignment between transmitter and receiver is required for these types of networks due to the highly atmospheric sensitivity of the THz system. And also, the THz indoor network deals with fluctuations of

hand, body, head (maybe even eye) movements [21]. One of the highest data-driven use cases for THz is virtual reality (VR) & Augmented reality games, which requires rapid body and hand movements. These movements in all directions end up with Six Degrees of Freedom (6DoF), borrowing the idea from the freedom of movement of an aircraft body [22] as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. 6DoF channel model for 6G indoor THz network

These 6DoF movements are up/down, left/right, backward/upward, yaw, pitch roll. For instance, there are particular movements for VR/AR specific games which are repeated quite often. Even in the case of walking in general, the human body recurs a particular pattern of movement with a specific velocity. In [23], we can see that normal human walking depends on "bobbing," i.e., the up and down movement of the body's center. The movement rate of bobbing is directly proportional to the velocity of the human. Thus, rapid walking is more susceptible to beam misalignments than slow walking. Moreover, while walking, the body's yaw, pitch, and roll motions emulate a sinusoidal wave [24]. Even when a human body is sedentary or standing tall, it leans to move in trivial amounts in all the 6DoF. Therefore, propagation modeling of this 6DoF movement on indoor networks will be an enormous challenge to solve for 6G.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we discuss with an overview the characteristics, measurement, and modeling of 6G wireless channels. Also, we provide a summary of recent advances in channel research of 6G. Finally, we outline the research challenges, open issues, and future direction of channel models and characteristics in 6G wireless communications.

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